

	DF	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	p value
Rep	6	255.82	42.64	8.576	0.0097**
Light	1	4.07	4.07	0.818	0.4006
Residuals	6	29.86	4.98		
Surface	3	80.49	26.832	3.798	0.0183
Light:Surface	3	12.68	4.227	0.598	0.6202
Residuals	36	254.32	7.064		

Table 1. Two-Way ANOVA of actinulae mechanosensory pilot study

Figure 1. Results of Mechanosensory pilot study in actinulae larvae

To identify which texture to use in the main settlement study along with the smooth (no texture) control, we performed a mechanosensory pilot study examining the effect of the control and the following three textures: Course, Medium, and Fine. The textures were generated by scratching Petri dishes with three different levels of sandpaper accordingly. To compare the effects of the textures on larval settlement, we performed a two-way ANOVA (Table S10) and found that the surface texture factor was significant ($p=0.0183$). We then performed a Tukey means comparison test to rank the four treatments and found that the control performed the best with a significance grouping of a, followed by the course treatment (ab significance group), and then the fine and medium treatments with significance groupings of b. Since the course texture performed the best out of the three, we chose to use this texture in our full larval settlement study.